

ExPaNDS Technical Note 1: Embedding PaNET in DataCite metadata

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Abstract

This note describes the recommended way to include PaNET terms within the DataCite description of a dataset.

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1. What is PaNET

PaNET is a collection of various terms describing experimental techniques conducting measurements based on radiation sources that generate scientific data. Such experimental techniques typically involve using specialist equipment to make observations about the target under investigation. The target may be placed in a controlled environment during the observation period.

The collection of techniques is organised into a hierarchy, where a technique may be identified as being a broader form of other techniques. It is not uncommon for PaNET to identify multiple (directly) broader techniques for some specific technique. This is because there are different ways in which a technique may be generalised.

Each PaNET term is identified with an Internationalized Resource Identifier or IRI¹ (which is, roughly speaking, a URL). In itself, the IRI is an opaque and persistent identifier (ID); however, PaNET also contains natural language labels for techniques. PaNET also contains links to external corpora that identify related terms.

The hierarchy of terms described in PaNET is organised using the Web Ontology Language (OWL) resulting in an ontology, i.e. a conceptualisation of the domain of experimental techniques.

The [PaNET ontology](#) is further documented in the document [doi:10.5281/zenodo.4806026](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4806026).

2. What is the DataCite metadata schema

DataCite is an organisation that is responsible for making a certain type of persistent identifier, called Digital Object Identifier (DOI), work with research data and other research outputs. Creating DOI for research outputs enable their citation and DataCite is one of the organisations endorsing the data citation principles². As part of their activity, DataCite

¹ RFC3987: <https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/html/rfc3987>

² <https://force11.org/info/joint-declaration-of-data-citation-principles-final/>

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defines and maintains a metadata schema³ that may be used to describe datasets and must be used when creating a DOI via their service.

The DataCite metadata schema is generic and it is represented as an XML schema. It does not directly include domain-specific metadata fields, as it is meant to cover datasets from all domains. However, the metadata schema contains elements that while generic, allow for inclusion of domain-specific values.

The DataCite metadata schema may be used in various scenarios. The main requirement is to include the metadata in the landing pages for the DOIs of the different research outputs.

Another such place is with the OAI-PMH protocol. OAI-PMH is a network protocol that allows a client to discover a list of available datasets and obtain metadata describing those datasets. OAI-PMH allows for a dataset to be described by multiple metadata schemata, with the OAI-PMH client choosing which schema(ta) to obtain. The DataCite metadata is a common choice, with several OAI-PMH servers and clients implementing support.

The DataCite has a Metadata Working Group that provides [documentation of the schema](#). DataCite also supports and maintains the mapping between DataCite and OAI-PMH.

3. Why embed PaNET in DataCite metadata

The scientific process through which a dataset was collected is one of the most fundamental aspects when describing the dataset.

One aspect when making a dataset FAIR is the requirement to make a dataset findable; that is, a scientist can find the dataset that matches her requirements. When searching for datasets, the experimental technique is often very important to the scientist. In addition, the hierarchical nature of the experimental techniques organised in PaNET allows a scientist to search for data collected using a broad PaNET term and receive datasets that are tagged with narrower PaNET terms. For example, 'x-ray absorption'⁴ and 'x-ray linear dichroism'⁵ are both examples of 'absorption technique'⁶, so searching for the more general term ('absorption technique') should retrieve all datasets tagged with any of the child terms. The PaNET ontology would also allow guided searching; for example, by prompting the scientist with broader and narrower terms that the scientist could use if a search produces too few or too many results (respectively).

Another aspect of FAIR is about making a dataset reusable. Often, understanding the experimental technique is critical when attempting to reuse the dataset in a different context. Therefore, this information is potentially useful when investigating a pre-selected dataset.

Simply including the experimental technique as a natural language in the dataset description provides a sub-optimal solution. Different scientists may use different phrases to describe

³ <https://schema.datacite.org/>

⁴ <http://purl.org/pan-science/PaNET/PaNET01227>

⁵ <http://purl.org/pan-science/PaNET/PaNET01300>

⁶ <http://purl.org/pan-science/PaNET/PaNET00202>

the same experimental technique (“CT” vs “computed tomography” vs “CT scan” vs “computed tomography scan” vs “computed axial tomography” vs ...); moreover, the choice of natural language is not guaranteed (“computed tomography” vs “computertomografie” vs “tomodensitométrie” and so on).

A scientist who is searching for data using a generic experimental technique may wish the results to include datasets described by a more specific (narrower) experimental technique. Including the experimental technique as a natural language makes supporting such searching hard and error-prone.

4. How to embed PaNET in DataCite metadata

This section describes how PaNET terms can be added to DataCite metadata.

The approach is to use existing DataCite metadata elements that allow for domain-specific information, in order to include PaNET terms. The enhanced dataset description is an XML document that conforms to the DataCite metadata schema.

Existing conforming DataCite metadata consumers should be able to process the enhanced metadata description with no changes. However, such consumers may ignore PaNET terms unless they are updated to take advantage of this additional information.

In the following technical description, the terms in capital letters (e.g., RECOMMENDED, SHOULD, SHOULD NOT and MUST) are taken from RFC 2119⁷.

For each PaNET term used for a given dataset, there SHOULD be a corresponding **subject** element in the DataCite metadata. Each PaNET subject element adheres to the following conditions:

- The element SHOULD have a **subjectScheme** attribute and that attribute SHOULD have the value **PaNET**.
- The element MUST have a **schemeURI** attribute and that attribute MUST have the value **http://purl.org/pan-science/PaNET/PaNET.owl**.
- The element MUST have a **valueURI** attribute and that attribute MUST be the purl.org IRI of the PaNET term; for example, **http://purl.org/pan-science/PaNET/PaNET01135** for ‘absorption spectroscopy’.
- The element MAY have a **classificationCode** attribute, which is RECOMMENDED to be the final path element of the PaNET term IRI; for example, **PaNET01135** is the recommended classificationCode for the PaNET term **http://purl.org/pan-science/PaNET/PaNET01135**.
- The element MAY have a value. If present, the value SHOULD be the preferred label for the PaNET term in the desired natural language.

The following example shows a **subject** element that identifies the PaNET term describing the “absorption spectroscopy” experimental technique.

⁷ <https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/html/rfc2119>


```
<subject subjectScheme="PaNET"
  schemeURI="http://purl.org/pan-science/PaNET/PaNET.owl"
  valueURI="http://purl.org/pan-science/PaNET/PaNET01135"
  classificationCode="PaNET01135"
>absorption spectroscopy</subject>
```

The following example provides a complete DataCite metadata description of a fictitious dataset ("Example Dataset"). In this example, ellipses ("[...]") are used as placeholder values. The example also includes the above single PaNET term, identifying that the dataset was obtained using absorption spectroscopy.

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
<resource xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance"
  xmlns="http://datacite.org/schema/kernel-4"
  xsi:schemaLocation="http://datacite.org/schema/kernel-4
    http://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.4/metadata.xsd">
  <identifier identifierType="DOI">10.5072/example-full</identifier>
  <creators>
    <creator><creatorName nameType="Personal">Jane
      Doe</creatorName></creator>
    <creator>[...]</creator>
  </creators>
  <titles>
    <title>Example Dataset</title>
  </titles>
  <subjects>
    <subject xml:lang="en" subjectScheme="PaNET"
      schemeURI="http://purl.org/pan-science/PaNET/PaNET.owl"
      valueURI="http://purl.org/pan-science/PaNET/PaNET01135"
      classificationCode="PaNET01135"
      >absorption spectroscopy</subject>
  </subjects>
  <resourceType resourceTypeGeneral="Dataset"
    >Dataset</resourceType>
</resource>
```

